

Load Service Capacity Evaluation of Reinforced Concrete Girder of the Gogo Tanjung Bridge Base on SNI-1725-2016 Code

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Abstract – The SNI 1725-2016 standard for concrete bridge design, which affects the girder beam design parameters, was introduced by Indonesia's Directorate General of Highways in 2017. This study intends to assess how well the updated bridge loading rule SNI-1725-2016 is being applied to the reinforced concrete girders of the existing Gogo Tanjung Bridge in the Padang Tiji sub-District of Pidie Regency, Aceh Province. The bridge measures 12 meters in length, 4 meters in width, and has girders that are 40 by 1 meters and 50 by 2 meters in size, respectively. The girder bridge's flexural moment, shear strength, deflection, and service capacity design were all tested in the study. In accordance with the findings of the SNI 1725-2016 study of the Gogo Tanjung concrete girder bridge, it can be drowned that the ultimate flexural moment value was 1581,95 kN.m in which less than allowed value of 1639,84 kN.m. The shear strength was 56,958 kN in which lower than permission value of 879,75 kN. The deflection value was 0,01995 m, which is marginally equal to the allowed value of 0,025 m. This indicates that the Gogo Tanjung concrete bridge girder was not able to perform current service capacity design.

Keywords: SNI 1726-2019, flexural moment, shear strength, deflection, service capacity design

Introduction

The bridge is a construction that connects one area to another, which is separated by rivers, hills, seas, highways, and railroads. The bridge is also one of the important facilities in human life (Supriyadi B., 2007). According to the types of bridge materials, it consists of concrete bridges, steel bridges, wooden bridges, and composite bridges. The most common bridge is a concrete bridge that uses concrete and reinforcement as the main material. Its design must also follow good regulations and specifications because bridges are a very important part of road infrastructure (Z. A. Bukhsh, et al., 2018). In Indonesia, load service capacity design for concrete bridge uses the RSNI T-02-2005. However, since July, 2017 the Indonesia Directorate General of Highways (BSN) has introduced an updated code of SNI 1725-2016 in accordance to No.05/SE/Db/2017(Bina Marga, 2017). This code has summarized the latest historical earthquake in Indonesia such as peak ground acceleration (pga) and soil types which effect on increase coefficient of elastic response (Csm) on the load factor of horizontal earthquake. This Csm effects on the increase of load in the structure elements of bridge which was required to evaluate the existing bridges.

In Aceh Province, the Gogo Tanjong concrete bridge at Padang Tiji subdistrict was designed by using the RSNI T-02-2005 which is classified as a class C bridge. The length of the bridge is 12 m and the floor width is 4 m and the sidewalk width is 2 m. x 0,50 m which was to be evaluated. One of the critical elements of this bridge is a main beam or girder. This is due to a girder is responsible for carrying the main load from the upper structure of bridge with covers of more than 50% of the total load. The structural analysis of the girder which covers the flexural moment, shear strength and deflection are three main parameters of girder that play an important role

in determining the serviceability of the existing bridge. This paper presents data on the flexural moment, shear strength and deflection of the Gogo Tanjong concrete girder in accordance with SNI 1725-2016.

Materials and Methods

SNI 1725:2016 Bridge Loading

Loads that are considered in bridge design are fixed loads, traffic loads, and the environment load. Fixed loads consist of structural dead loads, and additional dead loads. Traffic loads consist of lane loads, truck loads, and brake loads. The environmental loads consist of wind loads and earthquake loads.

According to SNI 1725-2016, the self-weight of a building is the weight structural elements and others. This includes the weight of materials and bridge parts which are fixed structural elements, plus non-structural. The additional dead load is the weight of all the materials that make up a load on the bridge.

The traffic load for bridge design consists of lane load D and truck load T. According to SNI 1725-2016 Lane load D acts on the entire width of the vehicle lane that affects the bridge. It is equivalent to an actual convoy of vehicles. The total load of lane D works depends on the width of the vehicle lane itself. The intensity of the "D" load consists of an evenly distributed load (BTR) combined with a concentrated line load (BGT) as shown in Figure 2.

Concentrated line load (BGT) with intensity p kN/m must be located perpendicular to the direction of traffic on the bridge. The intensity of p is 49.0 kN/m. To obtain the maximum negative bending moment in a continuous bridge, a second identical BGT must be positioned in the transverse direction of the bridge in the other span.

Figure 1. Lane load "D"

Figure 2. Load lane "D": BTR and burdened

Figure 3. Loading Truck "T"

A "T" truck load is one heavy vehicle with 3 axles located at various positions in the design traffic lane. Each axle consists of two loading contact areas which are intended to simulate the influence of heavy vehicle wheels. Only one "T" truck is assigned per design traffic lane.

According to SNI 1725-2016, the dynamic load factor (FBD) is the result of the interaction between a moving vehicle and a bridge. The magnitude of the FBD depends on the fundamental frequency of the vehicle suspension. It is usually between 2 and 5 Hz for heavy vehicles. For design, FBD is expressed as an equivalent static load. For "D" loading FBD is a function of the equivalent span length as shown in Figure 4. For single spans, the equivalent span length is taken to be equal to the actual span length. Meanwhile, for the loading of "T" trucks, FBD is taken as 30%. The calculated FBD value is used for all parts of the building that are above ground level. For substructure parts and foundations below the surface line, the FBD value shall be taken as a linear transition from the value at the ground level to zero at a depth of 2 m.

Figure 4. Dynamic load factor for load T for lane "D" loading

In SNI 1725-2016 the greatest brake force must be taken from 25% of the design truck axle weight or 5% of the design truck weight plus the lane load evenly distributed BTR. The brake force must be applied to all loaded design lanes containing traffic in the same direction. According to SNI 1725-2016, environmental actions include the effects of temperature, wind, floods, earthquakes, and other natural causes. Environmental influences that are considered include the influence of wind loads and earthquake loads. Wind load on the structure (EWs),

The total force of the wind load must not be taken less than 4,4 kN/mm on the compression plane and 2,2 kN/mm on the suction plane on the frame and arch structure, and not less than 4,4 kN /mm in beams or girders.

In the absence of more precise data, the design wind pressure in MPa can be determined using the following equation.

$$PD = PB \left(\frac{VDZ}{VB} \right) \quad (1)$$

Information:

PD = design wind pressure,

PB = basic wind pressure as specified in table 2.8,

VDZ = design wind speed at design elevation, Z (km/h),

VB = design wind speed, i.e. 90 to 126 km/h at an elevation of 1000 mm

The “EW” seismic load on the bridge must be planned so that it has a low probability of collapse but can suffer significant damage and disruption to services due to the earthquake with a probability of exceeding 7% in 75 years. Partial or complete replacement of the structure is required in some cases. Higher performance such as operational performance can be determined by the competent authorities.

The earthquake load is taken as the horizontal force which is determined based on the multiplication of the elastic response coefficient (Csm) with the equivalent structure weight which is then modified by the response modification factor (Rd) with the following formulation:

$$EQ = \frac{Cms}{Rd} \times Wt \quad (2)$$

Information:

EQ = the static horizontal earthquake force (kN)

Csm = the elastic earthquake response coefficient

Rd = the response modification factor

Wt = the total weight of the structure (kN)

The elastic response coefficient Csm was obtained from the bedrock acceleration map and the acceleration spectra according to the earthquake area and the design earthquake return period. The acceleration coefficient obtained based on the earthquake map is multiplied by an amplification factor according to the soil conditions to a depth of 30 m under the bridge structure. The calculation of the effect of an earthquake on the bridge including the earthquake load, in analysis, the earthquake map and structural details refer to SNI 2833:2016, an earthquake resistance planning standard for bridges.

Load Combination Based on SNI 1725:2016

The following are loading combinations based on SNI 1725: 2016, as shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Load Combination and Laod factor

Type of Load Combination	MS									<i>use one</i>		
	MA	TT										
	TA	TD	EU	EW _S	EW _L	BF	EU _n	TG	ES			
	PR	TB								EQ	TC	TV
	PL	TR										
	SH	TP										
Strength I	Y _p	1,80	1,00	-	-	1,00	0,50/1,20	Y _{TG}	Y _{ES}	-	-	-
Strength II	Y _p	1,40	1,00	-	-	1,00	0,50/1,20	Y _{TG}	Y _{ES}	-	-	-
Strength III	Y _p	-	1,00	1,40	-	1,00	0,50/1,20	Y _{TG}	Y _{ES}	-	-	-
Strength IV	Y _p	-	1,00	-	-	1,00	0,50/1,20	-	-	-	-	-
Strength V	Y _p	-	1,00	0,40	1,00	1,00	0,50/1,20	Y _{TG}	Y _{ES}	-	-	-
Extreme I	Y _p	Y _{Eq}	1,00	-	-	1,00	-	-	-	1,00	-	-
Extreme II	Y _p	0,50	1,00	-	-	1,00	-	-	-	-	1,00	1,00
Serviceability I	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,30	1,00	1,00	1,00/1,20	Y _{TG}	Y _{ES}	-	-	-
Serviceability II	1,00	1,30	1,00	-	-	1,00	1,00/1,20	-	-	-	-	-
Serviceability III	1,00	0,80	1,00	-	-	1,00	1,00/1,20	Y _{TG}	Y _{ES}	-	-	-
Serviceability IV	1,00	-	1,00	0,70	-	1,00	1,00/1,20	-	-	-	-	-
Fatigue (TD dan TR)	-	0,75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Analysis and Design of Bridge Structural Elements

The structural analysis of bridge girders uses certain static mechanics with the assumption that pin-pin beams are supported. Then for the design of reinforced concrete girder sections using the ultimate method, where the calculation limits the ultimate load to the nominal load limit.

According to McCormac (2000), For flexural strength, calculations use the ultimate method, where the ultimate load with the ultimate limit of a structural member that bears the bending moment about the strong axis, must fulfill the following equation:

$$M_u \leq \phi M_n \tag{3}$$

M_u = factored bending moment (kN.m)

M_n = nominal moment of section (kN.m)

ϕ = moment reduction factor

For the shear strength of beams, the calculation also uses the ultimate method, where the ultimate limit of a structural member that bears the shear force about the strong axis must fulfill the following equation, namely:

$$V_u \leq \phi V_n \tag{4}$$

V_u = factored shear force (kN)

V_n = sectional shear strength (kN)

ϕ = shear reduction factor

For the calculation of beam deflection, the calculation of certain static structural analysis, where the deflection that occurs due to load is compared with the allowable deflection limit for concrete bridge beams, and fulfills the following equation, namely:

$$\delta_{Max} < \delta_{clearance} = L/480 \tag{5}$$

δ_{Max} = deflection that occurs due to load (m)

δ_{permit} = allowable deflection (m)

L = Length of beam (m)

Evaluation method

To evaluate the loading and sectional capacity of existing bridges using SNI-1725-2016 regulations, this can be done using a flow chart as shown in Figure 5 below:

Figure 5. Flow chart of research methodology

Data collection

In this study, bridge data were obtained from the Public Works and Housing Office of Pidie District, Aceh Province. The data needed is in the form of bridge dimensions and quality of bridge materials.

1. Bridge superstructure data

The span length of the bridge,	L	= 12 m
The width of the road (traffic lane),	B1	= 4,0 m
The width of the sidewalk,	B2	= 0,5 m
The total width of the bridge,	B	= 5 m
Number of girders,	n	= 4
Bridge floor slab thickness,	ts	= 0,20 m
The thickness of the pavement slab,	tt	= 0,30 m
Asphalt layer thickness + overlay,	ta	= 0,08 m
Rain puddle height,	th	= 0,05 m
Side plane height,	ha	= 2,30 m
Distance between girders,	s	= 1,00 m
Girder dimensions, girder width,	b	= 0,40 m
Girder height,	h	= 1.00 m

a. Plan of Bridge

b. Cross Section of Bridge

Figure 6. Plan and Cross Section of Bridge

Structure material

Strength of Concrete, K-300 : ($f'c = 24.9 \text{ MPa}$)

Steel quality

- Steel quality for main reinforcement, $f_y = 390 \text{ MPa}$

- Quality of steel for stirrup reinforcement, $f_y = 240 \text{ MPa}$

Specific Gravity :

- Weight of reinforced concrete, $w_c = 25.00 \text{ kN/m}^3$

- Weight of unreinforced concrete, $w'c = 24.00 \text{ kN/m}^3$

- Weight of compacted asphalt, $w_a = 22.00 \text{ kN/m}^3$

- Specific gravity of water, $w_w = 9.80 \text{ kN/m}^3$

Results

Calculation Results and Structural Analysis

Based on the data above, after calculating the loading based on SNI 1725-2016 and structural analysis for reinforced concrete bridge girder beams, the results of the loading calculation are obtained as shown in Table 2.

Results of Calculation of Ultimate Moment on Bridge Girder

Based on the data in Table 3, it can be seen that the results of the calculation of the load combination for the moment on the bridge reinforced concrete girders, are obtained at the maximum value of the moment for the girders in the Strength I, which is a combination of dead load, additional dead load, truck load and brake force, with a value maximum moment for the girder, $M_u = 1581,95$ kN.m.

Table 2. Calculation Result of Ultimate Girder Moment Combination

No	Load type	M (kN.m)	Load Factor					Unit
			Strength I	Strength II	Strength III	Strength IV	Strength V	
1	Self Weight (MS)	261	339,3	339,3	339,3	339,3	339,3	kN.m
2	Additional Dead Weight (MA)	40,5	81	81	81	81	81	kN.m
3	Truck Load "T" (TI)	570,983	1027,77	799,376	-	-	-	kN.m
4	Brake Force (TB)	74,38	133,884	104,132	-	-	-	kN.m
5	Wind Load (Ew)	11,16	-	, -	15,624	-	4,464	kN.m
6	Earthquake Load (Eq)	180,9	-	-	-	-	-	kN.m
	Total (M)		1581,95	1323,81	435,924	420,3	424,764	kN.m

Table 3. Calculation Result of Ultimate Girder Moment Combination (advanced)

No	Load type	Load Factor						Unit
		Extreme I	Extreme II	Serviceability I	Service- ability II	Service- ability III	Service- ability IV	
1	Self Weight (MS)	339,3	339,3	261	261	261	261	kN.m
2	Additional Dead Weight (MA)	81	81	40,5	40,5	40,5	40,5	kN.m
3	Truck Load "T" (TI)	285,492	285,492	570,983	742,278	456,786	-	kN.m
4	Brake Force (TB)	37,19	37,19	74,38	96,694	59,504	-	kN.m
5	Wind Load (Ew)	-	-	3,348	-	-	7,812	kN.m
6	Earthquake Load (Eq)	180,9	-	-	-	-	-	kN.m
	Total (M)	923,882	742,982	950,211	1140,47	817,79	309,312	kN.m

Results of Calculation of Shear Force on Bridge Gider

Furthermore, based on the data in Table 4, it can be seen that the results of the calculation of the load combination for the shear force on the reinforced concrete girders of the bridge, are obtained at the maximum value of the shear force for the girders also in the Strong Combination I, which is a combination of dead load, additional dead load, truck load and force brakes, with the value of the maximum shear force for the girders, $V_u = 569,958$ kN.

Tabel 4. Results of Calculation of Shear Force on Bridge Gider

No	Load type	Load Factor					Unit	
		M (kN)	Strength I	Strength II	Strength III	Strength IV		Strength V
1	Self-Weight (MS)	87	113,1	113,1		113,1	113,1	kN
2	Additional Dead Weight (MA)	13,5	27	27	27	27	27	kN
3	Truck Load "T" (TT)	226,41	407,538	316,974	-	-	-	kN
4	Brake Force (TB)	12,4	22,32	17,36	-	-	-	kN
5	Wind Load (Ew)	3,72	-	-	5,208	-	1,488	kN
6	Earthquake Load (Eq)	60,3	-	-	-	-	-	kN
Total (V)			569,958	474,434	145,308	140,1	141,588	kN

Tabel 5. Results of Calculation of Shear Force on Bridge Gider (Advanced)

No	Load type	Load Factor						Unit
		Extreme I	Extreme II	Serviceability I	Serviceability II	Serviceability III	Serviceability IV	
1	Self-Weight (MS)	113,1	113,1	87	87	87	87	kN
2	Additional Dead Weight (MA)	27	27	13,5	13,5	13,5	13,5	kN
3	Truck Load "T" (TT)	113,205	113,205	226,41	294,333	181,128		kN
4	Brake Force (TB)	6,2	6,2	12,4	16,12	9,92		kN
5	Wind Load (Ew)	-	-	1,116	-	-	2,604	kN
6	Earthquake Load (Eq)	60,3	-	-	-	-		kN
Total (V)		319,805	259,505	340,426	410,953	291,548	103,104	kN

Calculation Result of Reinforced Concrete Girder Cross-sectional Capacity

Based on the results of the calculation of the cross-section design, it is obtained that the flexural reinforcement in tension on the girder size 400 x 1000 mm is 13 D 25 mm ($A_s = 6831.87 \text{ mm}^2$) and the compression reinforcement is 4 D 25 mm ($A_s = 1963.48 \text{ mm}^2$). Then from the results of the cross-sectional design with 13 D 25 mm reinforcement, the cross-section capacity of reinforced concrete girders is:

$$\phi M_n = 1639,84 \text{ kN.m} > M_u = 1581,95 \text{ kN.m} \text{ (OK)}$$

Then, based on the results of the calculation of the cross-sectional design, it is obtained that the shear reinforcement in the girder with a size of 400 x 1000 mm is dia. 10 – 100 mm in the beam support area, as well as dia. 10 – 150 mm in field area. Then from the results of the shear reinforcement design, it is obtained that the shear capacity of the cross-sectional capacity of reinforced concrete girders is:

$$\phi V_n = 879,75 \text{ kN} > V_u = 569,958 \text{ kN} \text{ (OK)}$$

Furthermore, based on the results of the calculation of the deflection of the girder beam measuring 400 x 1000 mm with a length of 12 m, the maximum deflection of the beam from various load combinations is obtained, namely:

$$\delta_{\text{Max}} = 0,01995 \text{ m} < \delta_{\text{clearance}} = L/480 = 12 \text{ m} / 480 = 0,025 \text{ m} \text{ (OK)}$$

Table 5. The results of checking the capacity and deflection of the girder

No	Description	Maximum Value	Allowed value	Unit	Status
1.	Moment of Girder	1581,95	1639,84	kN.m	OK
2.	Shear of Girder	569,958	879,75	kN	OK
3.	Deflection of Girder	0,01995	0,025	m	OK

Based on the results of the calculation of the moment and shear capacity of the cross-section and deflection of the girder beam measuring 400 x 1000 mm and length $L = 12$ m, that all design parameters of the girder beam meet the structural safety requirements, so that the beam is safe against working loads.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the SNI 1725-2016 evaluation on the Gogo Tanjung concrete girder bridge, it can be concluded that the ultimate flexural moment value was 1581,95 kN.m in which less than allowed value of 1639,84kN.m. The shear strength was 569,958 kN in which lower than permission value of 879,75 kN. The deflection value was 0,01995 m, which is marginally equal to the allowed value of 0,025 m. This indicate that the Gogo Tanjung concrete bridge girder was no longer able to perform current service capacity design.

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